

Correction

Correction: Elfadaly, A.; Abate, N.; Masini, N.; Lasaponara, R. SAR Sentinel 1 Imaging and Detection of Palaeo-Landscape Features in the Mediterranean Area. *Remote Sens.* 2020, 12, 2611

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The authors wish to make the following corrections to this paper [1]: Due to mislabeling, replace:

Figure 6. Typical Neolithic settlements in the Tavoliere delle Puglie: (a) settlement of Masseria Schifata; (b) settlement of Passo di Corvo [36].

With

Figure 6. Example of evidence of the ancient landscape and archaeological remains in Apulia: (i) blue lines represent palaeoriver; (ii) red lines represent the Neolithic settlements of Palmori and Schifata; (iii) orange lines represent roads; (iv) light blue lines represent hydromorphic marks related to an ancient marshy environment; (v) black and grey lines represent modern roads, channels and fields [14] Figure 5.

The authors would like to apologize for any inconvenience caused to the readers by these changes.

Reference

1. Elfadaly, A.; Abate, N.; Masini, N.; Lasaponara, R. SAR Sentinel 1 Imaging and Detection of Palaeo-Landscape Features in the Mediterranean Area. *Remote Sens.* **2020**, *12*, 2611. [[CrossRef](#)]

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